

Electoral outcomes, power outages and firm performance

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Abstract

Even though a wide range of literature explores how governments target public goods strategically, only a handful of papers examine whether these electorally-motivated distributive patterns have consequences on the real economy. With the use of Turkish electoral and firm-level data, this paper examines whether electoral factors affect the variation in power outages experienced by firms across Turkish regions. Our findings demonstrate that sales of the firms that were located in regions in which the incumbent party received more votes were disproportionately higher as these firms experienced relatively lower numbers and duration of power outages.

JEL codes: D72; L25; R11; R58

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INTRODUCTION

While public policy should be constructed over equity and efficiency concerns, evidence indicates that politicians might act on clientelist grounds by neglecting economic fundamentals. A growing literature examines the role of political factors in the allocation of public investment and the provision of different public services from the central government to the sub-national level (see e.g., Lambrinidis et al., 2005; Luca & Rodríguez-Pose, 2015; Kauder et al., 2016; Rodríguez-Pose et al., 2016; Garmann, 2018, Livert & Gainza, 2018; Burrier, 2019 among many others). Electoral strategies of governments are observed to be important in transport investment decisions of the central government (see e.g., Burgess et al., 2015) and provision of public goods such as electricity (Baskaran et al., 2015; Min, 2019).

Even though the above-mentioned papers explore how governments target public goods strategically, only a handful examine whether these electorally-motivated distributive patterns have consequences on the real economy (Asher and Novosad, 2017; Luca, 2016, 2018; Bircan and Saka, 2019). Moreover, the locality of electoral politics and political economy of regions have been a neglected line of research in regional studies (Martin, 2015). This remark is visible in the literature as there is still very limited evidence on the channels through which electoral factors shape regional development. This paper aims to explore whether electoral favoritism played any role in cross-regional variations in firm performance by examining the link between electoral factors and power outages experienced by firms across different regions in Turkey.

Even though the intervention of the Turkish central government in the economy has declined since the 1980s, still the central government has its role in influencing the business environment. For instance, Saka and Bircan (2019) demonstrated that businesses in provinces that are aligned with the ruling party have easier access to credit. Bugra and Savaskan (2014) suggest that changes in regulations favor businesses that are close to the ruling party. More closely to this paper's contribution, Özcan and Gündüz (2015) argued that the ruling Justice and Development Party (Adalet ve Kalkima Partisi, AKP) reshaped industry structures and nurtured a new breed of politically connected businesses in gas and electricity distribution between 2003 and 2013. In this paper, we test whether the central government's links with these private energy companies play a role in the variation in power outages experienced by firms across different regions in Turkey. In particular, we will explore whether electoral factors had any effect on the variation in power outages experienced by firms and also examine whether such disproportionate power outages across different regions affected firm performance at the regional level. To our knowledge, this is one of the first attempts to combine regional and firm dimensions of distributive politics in the same setup.

The remaining part of the paper is organized as follows. In the next section, we provide a discussion on distributive politics theories and offer the hypotheses of this paper. Section 3 provides an empirical strategy where we provide the details of econometric models, variables, and data. Section 4 presents the results and finally, section 5 concludes.

DISTRIBUTIVE POLITICS THEORIES, FIRM PERFORMANCE AND HYPOTHESES

Distributive politics theories have been extensively used in explaining a list of socioeconomic phenomena (Albertus, 2017). This section provides a brief discussion on these theories and set hypotheses based on these theories.

Central discussion on distributive politics stems from two pillars. (i) *The Core Hypothesis* asserts that incumbents target their support groups to strengthen the existing power (Cox & McCubbins, 1986). This strategy creates a pork-barrelling effect which benefits the own strongholds and punishes the foes of the incumbents (Johnston, 1977; Levitt & Synder, 1995; Levitt & Poterba, 1999; Golden & Picci, 2008; Solé Ollé & Sorribas-Navarro, 2008; Cox, 2009; Rodriguez-Pose et al., 2016; Asher & Novosad, 2017; Psycharis et al., 2019). A second approach that receives interest among scholars is (ii) *The Swing Hypothesis* that relies on the tactical behavior of the incumbents. Dixit & Londregan (1996) focus on the swing voters who are more likely to change their voting patterns based on reward-based incentives. This stream of literature argues that parties will preferentially allocate public funds to regions in which obtaining a seat is relatively easier or target voters that are likely to swing (Lindbeck & Weibull, 1987; Ward & John, 1999; Stokes, 2005). Corstange (2018) also argues that competition adjusts the targeting of parties to reach out to inelastic voters (voters that are less likely to swing or more expensive to 'buy' their votes). Similarly, political parties may target regions in which obtaining a seat requires less number of votes as parties try to maximize their seats in the parliament subject to their resource limitations (Calvo & Murillo, 2004; Golden & Min, 2013).

While these approaches find sizable interest in the political science literature, there is a growing body of work on the exact formulation of these approaches as testable hypotheses (Casas, 2018). For instance, Solé-Ollé & Sorribas-Navarro (2008), Arulampalam et al. (2009) argue that incumbents are prone to target aligned, swing regions that are ideologically and politically closer to their fundamentals. These discussions put-forward that the incumbent party tends to place more investment into regions in which ideologically close parties are competing with each other. A natural expectation is the rise of the marginal productivity of distributive politics since these voters are more likely to change their voting behaviors (Desposato, 2006; de la Calle & Roussias, 2012; Calvo & Murillo, 2013; Aytaç, 2014; Luca & Rodríguez-Pose, 2015; Alexander et al. 2016).

The existing literature on Turkish case also validates that the central government targets resources to favour or punish voters (Aytaç, 2014; Çarkoğlu & Aytaç, 2015; Luca, 2017; Luca & Rodríguez-Pose, 2015, 2019). Aytaç (2014) demonstrated that the incumbent party channels disproportionately more resources to districts with an ideologically close challenger. Using individual-level data, Çarkoğlu & Aytaç (2015) showed that AKP targeted its strong partisans, less educated individuals and urban residents. Examining the public expenditure allocations across Turkish provinces between 2005 and 2012, Luca & Rodríguez-Pose (2015) found that the incumbent party channelled public expenditures to reward its core constituencies, but the socioeconomic factors were also important determinants. On the other hand, Luca & Rodríguez-Pose (2019) analyzed the

determinants of the public transport investment across Turkish provinces and demonstrated that the incumbent party could also target regions in opposition holds to build a state-party image (see also Luca, 2017 for the central government bureaucracy's role in the management of public investment).

While political and regional science literature heavily examined the role of distributive politics in the allocation of public resources, the effect of distributive economics on local economy has been underexamined (see e.g., Asher and Novosad, 2017; Luca, 2016, 2018; Bircan and Saka, 2019 for the role of distributive politics on the local economy). For instance, in a recent contribution, Saka & Bircan (2019) demonstrated that the opposition areas in Turkey suffer drops in employment and firm sales. The channel is through the financial intermediation as the incumbent party uses state banks to increase credit in politically competitive provinces which have an incumbent mayor aligned with the ruling party, but reduce it in similar provinces with an incumbent mayor from the opposition parties. This paper aims to contribute to this stream of literature by examining the role of electoral factors on the firm performance through their effect on the quality of power provision across Turkish regions.

It has been well-documented that the political factors played a major role in the energy supply and distribution across Turkish provinces. Özcan and Gündüz (2015) investigate the post-2000s for the privatization experiences in the energy industry and suggest a sizable patronage regime where politically connected firms were successful in obtaining public procurement. Moreover, Mesut (2018) highlights

the regulative and institutional transformation of the energy sector by expressing the historical path-dependency of the state-business relations in Turkey. These recent discussions are in lieu of the prior discussions of Bugra and Savaskan (2014) as politically connected firms and the business units that stand close to the incumbents will have better access in most of the public services. In the electricity industry, we argue that politically connected firms will have better access to electricity usage through various channels. Our central argument is the influence of the local political environment on the quality of the electricity services given at the firm level. Following Özcan & Gündüz (2015), we argue that the privatized nature of the electricity industry does not impede the extent of distributive politics. As the privatization process is already politically motivated, local distribution of electricity supply is also expected to be politically biased towards politically connected firms. Regardless of the public-private share of the electricity distribution, the overall process is politically motivated in Turkey (Özcan & Gündüz, 2015; Mesut, 2018).¹

Among various dimensions, there exists a related stream of literature that showed the negative effect of power outages on firm performance. Cole et al. (2018) find a negative association between power outages and firms' sales in Sub-Saharan African countries, with a stronger effect for firms that do not own a generator. Fisher-Vanden et al. (2015) find that Chinese firms re-optimize among inputs due to electricity scarcity, which then leads to increased costs of production. This increased cost of production resulted in worse performance for those firms that experienced an electricity shortage. Similarly, Geginat & Ramalho (2018) show that increased cost

and time for obtaining electricity hampered the performance of firms. Finally, Allcott et al. (2016) demonstrate that the level of electricity shortages reduces the plant's revenues and producer surplus resulting in lower economic performance. Similar to these discussions, we examine whether the power outages affect firm performance in Turkey while controlling for various other factors affecting firm performance. Additionally, given the possible reverse mechanisms and the omission of other factors, we use the instrumental variable approach to account for potential endogeneity.

Based on this contextualization, we construct four hypotheses to examine the influence of distributive politics on the regional economic environment.

H1: Governments have incentives to target core supporting regions, and therefore incumbent party stronghold regions would receive better electricity supply, and firms in these regions would experience fewer numbers and shorter periods of power outages.

H2: Incumbent party favors voters in regions with tight electoral contests (or close race), and these regions would receive a better provision of electricity, and firms there would experience fewer numbers and shorter periods of power outages.

H3: Regions with higher percentages of the electoral that are ideologically close to the incumbent party's position would experience fewer numbers and shorter periods of power outages.

H4: Firm performance is negatively associated with power outages.

EMPIRICAL STRATEGY

Econometric analysis model, variables and data

We use firm-level data from the Turkish Regional Enterprise Survey, which is conducted by the World Bank in 2015. Even though the World Bank collected firm-level data in Turkey for the previous years (2005, 2008 and 2013), the panel data that tracks the same firms over the entire period is limited. Furthermore, these surveys only use aggregate geographical clusters (five or six aggregated geographic clusters) for firms' location compared to the 26 NUTS II-level regions in the 2015 survey (see Appendix Table A1 for the NUTS II- and III-level classification of Turkish regions).² Therefore, this study uses firm-level data collected in 2015 to test the above set hypothesis.

The following model is proposed to check for the factors contributing to the power outages (PO) experienced by firms:

$$(PO)_{ij} = \beta_1 E_j + \beta_2 X_j + \beta_3 F_i + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

where i and j denote firms and regions, respectively. $(PO)_{ij}$ represents one of our three power outages measures: i) PO dummy: whether a firm experienced a power outage or not, ii) PO frequency: the number of power outages experienced by a firm in a given month, and iii) PO duration: average duration of these power outages.

Appendix Table A2 gives details on how firm-level variables are constructed, E_j is a vector of electoral variables in province j , X_j is a vector of socioeconomic variables in region j that may affect the power outage measures, while F_i is a vector of firm-

specific factors that may affect the power outage measures, and finally ε_i is the error term.

As discussed in section 2, state-business relationships could affect the quality of public service provision. For instance, the central government used regulations and public procurements during the privatization process of electricity networks (Özcan & Gündüz, 2015). Henceforth, the central government would have a close relationship with such private companies and could request them (or use its powers to put pressure on these companies) to provide a better supply of electricity in regions that are deemed to be vital for their survival. To test the hypotheses set in section 2, we use three electoral variables. We use the percentage of the vote share of the incumbent party (AKP) in 2011 parliamentary elections across regions to test the first hypothesis. In order to test the second hypothesis, we use the negative absolute value of the difference between the percentage votes of the incumbent party and its main challenger in each NUTS II region. Higher values for the electoral competition proxy represent tighter competition. Finally, to test the third hypothesis, we include a close competitor variable, which is an interaction between electoral competition variable and a dummy variable, which takes a value of 1 if AKP had a tight race with an ideologically close party and zero otherwise. Appendix Table A3 presents a detailed measurement of electoral variables.³

We also control for a number of regional factors that may affect the power outages. Power outages may be related to the overall supply of and demand for energy across Turkish regions. For instance, an unexpected increase in aggregate

demand for electricity could lead to power outages due to overloading (Henneaux, 2015). To account for overall energy demand, we use the gross domestic product (GDP) per capita and aggregate population. On the other hand, the variation in some of the power outages experienced by firms could be down to the quality of electrical infrastructure across different regions (Smith, 2004). To control for this, we use the total consumption of electricity across different regions as the overall consumption could be a proxy for the quality of electricity provision infrastructure. Similarly, we use the percentage of the population living in rural areas to account for the potential differences in costs per infrastructure unit between highly and sparsely populated areas. Finally, we also use the total public investment per 1000 inhabitants across Turkish regions to control for the central government's infrastructure investment as this could directly affect the quality of electricity infrastructure.⁴

Finally, we also control for three firm-specific factors that were found to be relevant for power outages. Following Alby et al. (2013), we control for the size of the firm as relatively larger firms may be located either in areas with more reliable energy supply or firms may have increased their firm size due to increased outages. On the other hand, Cole et al. (2018) suggest that firms that have a high level of electricity dependency will choose to locate in areas that have a more reliable electricity supply. Therefore, as a proxy for a firm's energy demand, we control for the industry that a firm belongs to based on the International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC). We include dummies for transportation, construction, metal, food, wholesale, textile, and other manufacturing and services to control for the line of industry. Finally, we

include a dummy variable that equals to one if a firm either owns a generator or firm's electricity came from a solar installation or alternative energy source. The likelihood of firms using alternative energy sources is expected to be higher if they experience relatively higher power outages from the general grid.

Based on the three measures of power outages, we first estimate a Probit regression when we use the power outage dummy variable as our dependent variable. We then estimate a zero-truncated Poisson (ZTP) and zero-inflated negative binomial regression (ZINBR) models for those firms who experienced a power outage (i.e., when we use power outage frequency and duration variables as our dependent variables). Figures A1 and A2 provide the frequency distribution for the number of power outages and duration of power outages experienced by firms, respectively. Since the distribution of the power outage frequency and duration data are overdispersed, we use in our analysis the ZTP and ZINBR models. Note that we do not prefer to use a Poisson regression model or a negative binomial regression model as analysis without truncation may bias the inferences.

Once we examine the potential determinants of power outages, we proceed to check for the influence of power outages on firm performance. We explore the determinants of firm performance by using the following estimation model:

$$(\text{Sales})_{ij} = \alpha + \beta_1(\text{PO}_{ij}) + \beta_2 Z_i + I_i + R_j + \varepsilon_i \quad (2)$$

where i and j denote firms and regions, respectively. $(\text{Sales})_{ij}$ is the total sales of firm i that is located in region j in the 2014 fiscal year. PO_{ij} is one of the three

power outage measures. Z_i is a vector of standard firm-specific factors that affect firm performance (Bernard et al., 2007; Greenaway & Kneller, 2007; Seker, 2012; Seker & Yang, 2014; Cole et al., 2018, among many others). These factors include the size and age of the firm, whether the firm has some foreign ownership, exports its sales, uses a generator and/or alternative energy sources to generate its electricity for production, engages with innovation and R&D activities, has financial and credit access, and whether the firm competes against unregistered or informal firms. I_i is the industry dummies and R_j is the region dummies; and ε_i is the error term (see Table A4 for the descriptive statistics).

One of the main problems that empirical studies should address is the possibility that both power outage measures and incumbent party vote shares could be endogenous. First, there are possible unobservable factors that may affect both power outages and electoral factors. Second, electoral outcomes in 2011 are likely to be affected by firm performances and power outages experienced in earlier periods. Therefore, voters may reward or punish governing parties based on their prior experiences (Larcinese et al., 2012). Third, power outage measures may be biased due to measurement error as these measures are self-reported. This measurement error could potentially lead to a downward attenuation bias of the estimated coefficients (see e.g., Alby et al., 2013; Cole et al., 2018, for similar discussions).⁵ Hence, to find a causal relationship between AKP vote shares and power outages, we construct a shift-share instrumental variable proposed by Luca (2016) for the AKP vote share (see also Luca & Rodríguez-Pose, 2019). The 2002 parliamentary election

in Turkey is considered as exogenous and a turning point in Turkish politics (see Luca (2016) for a detailed discussion on the instrumental variable). Construction of this variable assumes that the national vote pattern changes are party-specific, but external to an individual province reflect exogenous political shocks for that province. The instrumental variable for AKP vote shares is constructed by weighting n_{ib} , which represents the initial electoral result for each region (NUTS II) i in the base year b (2002), considering the national variation of AKP vote shares between 2011 and 2002 (N_{2011} and N_{2002} represent the national vote shares of AKP in 2011 and 2002 elections, respectively) and it is given below:

$$POL_{IV,i} = n_{i,2002} \left(1 + \frac{N_{2011} - N_{2002}}{N_{2002}} \right) \quad (3)$$

We also use the shift-share instrumental variable for AKP vote shares as an instrumental variable for the PO variables when we use firm performance as our dependent variable. Our argument is that this instrumental variable explains PO variables through its effect on the AKP vote shares in 2011, but it would not affect firm sales in 2014.

RESULTS

Electoral factors and power outages

Table 1 presents the results for three power outage measures as dependent variables where we test whether the electoral variables played a significant role in power outages experienced by firms. Columns (1)-(5) provide results when AKP vote share is used to test the core hypothesis (H1), and columns (6)-(10) offer the results

when we used the electoral competition and close competitor variables to test the swing hypotheses (H2 & H3).

<Insert Table 1 approximately here>

Starting with the core hypothesis, column (1) of Table 1 reports results based on estimations of an instrumental variable probit (IVProbit) model when the PO dummy is the dependent variable. A Wald test of the exogeneity of the instrumented variable suggests a rejection of the null hypothesis of no endogeneity at the 1% level. This highlights that the IVProbit model is a better fit for the analysis compared to the Probit model. Columns (2) and (3) report a zero-truncated poisson (ZTP) and a zero-inflated negative binomial regression (ZINBR) models, respectively. These models use PO frequency as a dependent variable only for the firms that reported power outages. We use the shift-share instrumental variable for AKP vote shares (IV-ZTP and IV-ZINBR), respectively. Finally, we report the results based on estimations on IV-ZTP and IV-ZINBR in columns (4)-(5), respectively, when PO duration variable is used as a dependent variable (see Appendix Table A5 for the results obtained without using an instrumental variable for AKP vote shares). The likelihood ratio tests suggest that the ZINBR models are preferable compared to ZTP models for handling zero-inflated and overdispersed PO frequency and duration data. According to the results presented in column (1), firms are more (less) likely to experience power outages in regions in which the AKP obtained fewer (more) votes. Furthermore, the estimations based on IV-ZINBR suggest that if a firm is located in a region where AKP got one percent more votes, the expected number of PO frequency and hour of

duration would decrease by a factor of 0.966 and 0.990 (i.e., 3.4% and 1%), respectively.⁶ For instance, a firm located in Ankara (where AKP vote share in 2011 parliamentary election was 49.2%) would experience 42.16% and 12.4% less frequent and duration of power outages compared to a firm located in Izmir (where AKP vote share in 2011 parliamentary election was 36.8%), respectively. Overall, these results confirm the first hypothesis where the core voting regions of AKP obtained relatively better electricity supply (or lower number and duration of power outages).

Next, we move to test the second and third hypotheses related to swing theory. Columns (6)-(10) report the results when we used the electoral competition and close competitor variables. We find that electoral competition increased the likelihood of power outages (column 6). When PO frequency and duration variables are used as dependent variables, the likelihood ratio tests suggest that the ZINBR models are preferable compared to the ZTP models. These results indicate that the frequency and the duration of these power outages are significantly higher in regions where the electoral competition was higher (columns 8 and 10, respectively). This could originate from the fact that the electoral competition and AKP vote shares are highly and negatively correlated. On the other hand, considering the firms in regions where the electoral competition was with an ideologically close competitor, the chance of realizing power outage, and the frequency and duration of power outages are relatively lower. Note that the coefficient of close competitor variable is negative and that the electoral competition and close competitor variable are jointly significant at the 5% level. Solé-Ollé & Sorribas-Navarro (2008), Arulampalam et al.

(2009) highlight the importance of alliances for swing voters. Likewise, Brown et al. (2011) argue that the opposition politicians may have a strong incentive to ignore corrupt practices by the government if the probability of future coalition-building is high. On the contrary, oppositions representing more ideologically distinct platforms will be less likely to enter into coalitions and could act as checks and balances. Therefore, the incumbent potentially did not engage in politically connected state-business relationships in regions where there was high electoral competition, but this was less of an issue in regions where the close competitor is also ideologically close. Therefore, our findings suggest that the second hypothesis does not hold as the incumbent does not favor regions where there is a tight electoral contest. However, our results validate that firms received more reliable energy provision in regions where there is an ideologically close competitor. This suggests the approval of our third hypothesis.⁷

Considering the other control variables, our results suggest that relatively larger firms are more likely to experience a power outage. Moreover, for larger firms, the frequency and duration of such power outages are also higher compared to smaller firms. However, we find that the likelihood of power outages is declining with the size of the firm. This finding is in line with the conclusions of Alby et al. (2013) on firm size. On the other hand, firms that use alternative energy production means are more likely to experience a power outage and more frequent power outages. Note that the duration of these power outages was shorter. This is an intuitive finding, suggesting that firms that are more likely to face power outages are more likely to

use alternative means of power production. Furthermore, the duration of power outages for these firms would be less as they use alternative energy production as a back-up option. On the other hand, the effect of other regional variables on power outages depends on the variable used to define power outages. A careful inspection of the data verifies that this is possibly due to the multicollinearity problem as the correlation coefficients among regional control variables are relatively high.⁸ These variables are included in the regression analysis as additional controls, but their exclusion from the models does not alter the relationship between electoral variables and power outage measures (see Appendix Table A7 for the relationship between electoral factors and power outage measures when regional control variables are excluded from the analysis).⁹

We also carried out an additional set of robustness analysis for the relationship between the electoral variables and the PO measures. Firstly, the power outages and the frequency and duration of these power outages that firms experienced in 2014 may be related to longer-term state-business relations. Özcan and Gündüz (2015) demonstrated that the AKP government nurtured a new breed of politically connected businesses in gas and electricity distribution networks between 2003 and 2013. Even though we cannot track the power outages experienced by firms due to data availability, we use average vote share of the AKP in 2002, 2007 and 2011 parliamentary elections, and electoral competition and close competitor variables. The results are presented in Table A8. When electoral variables are

obtained by using 2002, 2007, and 2011 parliamentary elections, the results are consistently similar to those shown in Table 1.

Power outages and firm performance

Table 2 reports the results for the regression on firm sales where different PO measures are used as independent variables. Columns (1) – (4), columns (5) – (8), and columns (9) – (12) of Table 2 report the results when we use PO dummy, PO frequency, PO duration variables as explanatory variables, respectively. First, second, third, and fourth columns of each separate scenario report regressions on firm sales using the pooled OLS, pooled OLS with industrial dummies, pooled OLS with both industrial and regional dummies, and two-stage least squares (2SLS) models where we further control for endogeneity. Table 2 also reports the first-stage F-statistics when PO measures are instrumented with shift-share AKP vote shares. Note that, F-statistics in all scenarios are well above ten, suggesting that our results do not suffer from weak instrument problem.

<Insert Table 2 approximately here>

According to the different estimated models, all PO measures show a negative and significant relationship with firm sales. Our findings are in line with Allcott et al. (2016) and Cole et al. (2018), where they also found that the absolute magnitude of the negative effect of PO measures on firm sales are relatively larger compared to the baseline OLS estimations. Based on the 2SLS estimates, our results suggest that the firms that experience power outage had 47% lower sales compared to firms that did not experience a power outage. On the other hand, a percentage increase in the

number of PO and duration of power outages is associated with 0.27% and 0.63% decrease in firm sales, respectively.

Beyond the variables of interest, the results suggest that manager's experience and education affect firm sales positively and significantly in all classifications highlighting the importance of the human capital for firm sales. Similarly, firms that have alternative energy production means tend to perform better compared to firms that do not have alternative energy production mechanisms. On the other hand, firms that had a sole owner tend to perform relatively worse as Seker and Yang (2014) argues that the sole proprietors tend to take fewer risks or pursue fewer opportunities due to full liability. In line with the findings of Bernard et al. (2007) and Greenaway & Kneller (2007), Seker & Yang (2014) and Cole et al. (2018), results suggest that firms that directly export have higher sales compared to non-exporting firms. Finally, firms that have access to overdraft facilities and credit lines, and spent on formal research and development activities (R&D) have higher sales compared to firms that do not have access to overdraft and loan and did not spend on R&D activities, respectively. Similarly, relatively larger firms and younger firms perform better compared to the smaller and older firms, which could be down to economies of scale and innovation prospects of firms, respectively.

When we combine the results obtained in Table 1 and 2, a percent increase in incumbent party votes decreases the PO frequency and duration by 3.4% and 1%, which then reduces sales by 0.92% and 0.63%, respectively. To quantify such an effect on the provinces, sales of a firm located in Izmir are 11.4% and 7.8% lower compared

to a firm located in Ankara due to the differences in number of PO frequency and duration experienced in these regions, respectively. As highlighted by Özcan & Gündüz (2015), the vast majority of the electricity distribution privatization between 2003 and 2013 was won by AKP-connected firms. Naturally, the governing party could favor its strongholds by requesting these privatized energy firms to provide a better provision of electricity in their stronghold regions. The findings of this paper confirmed such mechanism and that the political favoritism through the privatization of the energy networks also had a direct effect on the firms where the sales of firms that are located in AKP strongholds were found to be relatively better due to lower power outages.¹⁰

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we quantify the effect of distributive politics on firm performance through its impact on power outages. Combining Turkish electoral data with regional firm-level data, we demonstrate that the electoral factors play a role in the number and duration of power outages experienced by the firms in different regions in Turkey. Our final set of findings confirm that this process affects their economic performance that we measure by firm sales and sales growth.

Overall, our results suggest that the level of quality of electricity used by firms depends on the location of the firm. Those firms that locate in stronghold regions of the incumbent political party (AKP) realize lower electricity outages. While the impact of local electoral competition does not directly influence power outages, our

additional results show that incumbent favors those regions that are battleground areas with ideologically close competitors. Our second set of results highlights that electricity outage is an important constraint for firm performance. Overall, those firms realizing more frequent and more extended electricity outage are not performing well on average. This translates into the fact that the direct influence of distributive politics on electricity usage has spillover effects on firm-level economic performance. Given the variation of the distributive politics at the local electoral constituencies, our results highlight that electricity distribution stands as a vital mediating tool for the working of distributive politics in Turkey.

We believe our results shed light on the impact of distributive economics on regional development through its effect on firm performance. The findings also demonstrate support for pork-barrel politics as the firms in regions where the incumbent party received more votes tend to perform better. Additionally, there is also evidence of the positive spillover of distributive politics among battleground areas with closer ideological fundamentals. These combined results validate that distributive politics can work in a broader spectrum that exceeds the direct provision of public services and the distribution of public funds. Additional crony relations that affect the state-business relations are effective in countries like Turkey, where incumbents influence daily economic life through its impact on public and private institutions.

This paper examined the effect of the privatization of gas and electricity distribution across Turkish regions on the electricity outages experienced by firms, and how electoral factors played a role in this relation. However, a promising future research area is to examine how privatization may influence the allocation of private and public infrastructure investment across space and time and the distributional outcomes achieved by different economic agents. Hence, there may be other mechanisms through which privatization could affect regional development, which is worth exploring in future studies.

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¹ In this paper, we theorize the interlinkage between electoral factors and privatization (state business relationships), and the effect of this on the power outages experienced by firms across Turkish provinces. However, it should be noted that privatization could influence both the private and public investment across space (see, e.g., Estrin et al., 2009 for review of the effects of privatization), which could then affect distributional outcomes (see, e.g., Birdsall and Nellis, 2003).

² The firm-level data is from the World Bank Enterprise Survey

(www.enterprisesurveys.org).

³ The parliamentary elections are held at the NUTS III level in Turkey and to align our electoral variables with that of firm-level variables (i.e., NUTS II level), we collate the electoral results from NUTS III to NUTS II level.

⁴ All the socio-economic variables are obtained by taking the averages between 2012 and 2014 to avoid any business cycle effects (see Appendix Table A3 for the details of the socio-economic variables).

⁵ Some of these measurement errors could be related with perception bias. In regions in which the incumbent party is supported less, firms may be more likely to report higher power outages. The authors acknowledge this potential perception bias, but there is no mechanism that we could control for such potential perception bias, and the instrumental variable estimation would tackle this potential endogeneity.

⁶ The change in expected numbers of PO frequency and hours of PO duration could be obtained by using the exponentials of the coefficients of the AKP vote share in column (3) and (5) of Table 1, respectively.

⁷ We also carried out analysis when AKP vote shares, electoral competition and close competitor variables are included to the analysis simultaneously (see Appendix Table A6 for the detailed estimation results). When these variables are included simultaneously, AKP vote share variable is no longer significant, but the findings concerning electoral competition and close competitor variables are similar to those reported in Table 1. A careful inspection of the data verifies that this is possibly due to the multicollinearity problem. The correlation coefficient of electoral competition

and AKP vote share is -0.89. Hence, when we analyze the significance of electoral competition, we do not control for the AKP vote share in the analysis to avoid potential multicollinearity problem.

⁸ For instance, GDP per capita is negatively correlated with investment per 1000 people and rural variables (correlation coefficients -0.35 and -0.67, respectively). On the other hand, GDP per capita is positively correlated with the population and energy consumption (correlation coefficients of 0.55 and 0.81, respectively).

⁹ The power outage measures may be related to longer-term public investment stocks as the public investment may have improved electricity infrastructure quality over time. To control for such effect, we also included the public investment per 1000 people between 2003 and 2014 (during the ruling period of the AKP) in our analysis. However, the public investment levels for the 2012-2014 period and the 2003-2014 period are highly and positively correlated (i.e., a correlation coefficient of 0.74). Therefore, we found that the public investment per 1000 people between 2003 and 2014 is not significant when this variable is included with the variable measuring the public investment per 1000 people between 2012 and 2014. In sum, we argue that using a public investment stock variable that considers a more extended period does not alter the baseline results. The results are available upon request from authors.

¹⁰ Even though we controlled for many standard set of control variables in our analysis, there are potentially other factors that may affect firm sales. Moreover, firm performance could also be measured by using firm sales growth (see e.g., Seker & Yang, 2014 Grillitsch & Nilsson, 2017). We carried out a similar set of analysis by

including initial firm sales levels in 2012 as part of the control variables, which would be a good indicator for the stock position of the firm prior to the power outages experienced in 2014. Additionally, we used the sales growth between 2012 and 2014 as our dependent variable. The results from 2SLS regressions are presented in Table A9. Our results are similar to those reported in Table 2 where the variables of interest (i.e., PO measures) are negatively and significantly associated with firm sales growth.

Table 1. Determinants of power outage (PO) measures										
Dependent variable	Hypothesis 1: Core hypothesis					Hypotheses 2 and 3: Swing hypothesis				
	PO dummy	PO frequency		PO duration		PO dummy	PO frequency		PO duration	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Variables	IVProbit	IV-ZTP	IV-ZINBR	IV-ZTP	IV-ZINBR	Probit	ZTP	ZINBR	ZTP	ZINBR
AKP vote share	-0.0159*** (0.00220)	-0.0283*** (0.00153)	-0.0348*** (0.00436)	-0.00784*** (0.00188)	-0.0101* (0.00593)					
Electoral competition						0.00842*** (0.00177)	0.0211*** (0.00134)	0.0251*** (0.00361)	0.00812*** (0.00136)	0.00985** (0.00393)
Close competitor						-0.00215 (0.00154)	-0.00241* (0.00124)	-0.00119 (0.00329)	-0.000864 (0.00145)	-0.00265 (0.00410)
Log (Worker)	0.193*** (0.0364)	0.147*** (0.0264)	0.149** (0.0670)	0.163*** (0.0333)	0.130 (0.0887)	0.195*** (0.0364)	0.155*** (0.0265)	0.167** (0.0673)	0.150*** (0.0326)	0.149* (0.0887)
Log (Worker)^2	-0.0334*** (0.00700)	-0.0127*** (0.00464)	-0.00658 (0.0114)	-0.0260*** (0.00618)	-0.0252* (0.0151)	-0.0337*** (0.00700)	-0.0151*** (0.00463)	-0.0112 (0.0115)	-0.0224*** (0.00600)	-0.0260* (0.0150)
Alternative energy	0.473*** (0.0529)	0.123*** (0.0287)	0.0992 (0.0833)	-0.403*** (0.0455)	-0.348*** (0.120)	0.474*** (0.0530)	0.139*** (0.0287)	0.141* (0.0840)	-0.420*** (0.0447)	-0.508*** (0.117)
GDP per capita	0.930*** (0.0888)	-1.391*** (0.0592)	-1.801*** (0.183)	-0.320*** (0.0812)	-1.184*** (0.307)	0.928*** (0.0936)	-1.234*** (0.0609)	-1.668*** (0.191)	-0.411*** (0.0844)	-1.303*** (0.314)
Public investment per 1000 people	-0.126* (0.0648)	0.210*** (0.0467)	0.182 (0.137)	-0.322*** (0.0726)	-0.602*** (0.206)	-0.163** (0.0668)	0.219*** (0.0480)	0.161 (0.141)	-0.383*** (0.0766)	-0.471** (0.212)
Rural	0.0218*** (0.00263)	0.00541*** (0.00173)	0.00713 (0.00529)	0.0405*** (0.00227)	0.0371*** (0.00716)	0.0204*** (0.00288)	-0.00671*** (0.00195)	-0.00436 (0.00573)	0.0458*** (0.00258)	0.0412*** (0.00762)
log (Population)	0.584*** (0.0492)	-0.433*** (0.0336)	-0.696*** (0.0926)	-0.224*** (0.0396)	-0.683*** (0.138)	0.572*** (0.0524)	-0.597*** (0.0360)	-0.926*** (0.0985)	-0.147*** (0.0444)	-0.621*** (0.145)
log (Energy consumption)	-0.308*** (0.0611)	0.584*** (0.0374)	0.761*** (0.119)	0.816*** (0.0581)	1.472*** (0.190)	-0.331*** (0.0646)	0.457*** (0.0378)	0.684*** (0.125)	0.866*** (0.0621)	1.596*** (0.198)
Log-likelihood	-3530.35	-6809.4317	-4340.475	-6113.9131	-3056.58	-3546.93	-6829.52	-4341.68	-6102.34	-3054.23
Wald test of exogeneity (Chi-square)	21.08									
P-value of the exogeneity test	0.0000									
LR test of alpha=0			4937.91		6114.66			4975.68		6096.22
P-value LR test			0.0000		0.0000			0.0000		0.0000
Joint significance (Chi-square)						23.99	294.67	63.01	47.43	7.29
p-value (joint significance)						0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0261
Observations	5,931	2,158	2,158	2,083	2,083	5,931	2,158	2,158	2,083	2,083

Notes: Industry dummies and constants are included in all regressions, but are not reported. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. ***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% level, respectively. Results in columns (1-5) were obtained with the use of instrumental variables (IV) estimation, where the AKP vote shares are instrumented with the shift-share IV.

Table 2. Determinants of firm performance												
VARIABLES	PO variable: PO dummy				PO variable: PO frequency				PO variable: PO duration			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)
PO variable	-0.0857*** (0.0304)	-0.0998*** (0.0307)	-0.0613** (0.0309)	-0.477** (0.214)	-0.0663*** (0.0211)	-0.0741*** (0.0210)	-0.0462** (0.0206)	-0.268*** (0.102)	-0.0468* (0.0255)	-0.0591** (0.0255)	-0.0365* (0.216)	-0.628*** (0.220)
Manager experience	0.0805*** (0.0261)	0.0641** (0.0258)	0.0382 (0.0250)	0.0698*** (0.0265)	0.0738*** (0.0268)	0.0577** (0.0266)	0.0307 (0.0257)	0.0552** (0.0270)	0.0660** (0.0272)	0.0507* (0.0269)	0.0276 (0.0261)	0.0502* (0.0283)
Manager education	0.124*** (0.0236)	0.117*** (0.0236)	0.113*** (0.0228)	0.118*** (0.0240)	0.115*** (0.0243)	0.107*** (0.0243)	0.101*** (0.0235)	0.104*** (0.0246)	0.111*** (0.0246)	0.102*** (0.0246)	0.0960*** (0.0238)	0.0993*** (0.0258)
Sole ownership	-0.168*** (0.0422)	-0.162*** (0.0418)	-0.0124 (0.0421)	-0.149*** (0.0430)	-0.167*** (0.0436)	-0.162*** (0.0432)	0.00371 (0.0436)	-0.139*** (0.0454)	-0.173*** (0.0442)	-0.169*** (0.0438)	-0.00678 (0.0442)	-0.114** (0.0508)
Foreign ownership	0.129 (0.187)	0.153 (0.182)	0.259 (0.196)	0.167 (0.171)	0.138 (0.198)	0.167 (0.192)	0.314 (0.207)	0.170 (0.177)	0.127 (0.198)	0.159 (0.193)	0.293 (0.208)	0.244 (0.187)
Export	0.302*** (0.0664)	0.264*** (0.0670)	0.219*** (0.0700)	0.276*** (0.0690)	0.305*** (0.0672)	0.270*** (0.0676)	0.225*** (0.0709)	0.268*** (0.0702)	0.329*** (0.0692)	0.295*** (0.0697)	0.253*** (0.0728)	0.328*** (0.0757)
Log (Age)	-0.167** (0.0766)	-0.166** (0.0760)	-0.0413 (0.0720)	-0.180*** (0.0676)	-0.167** (0.0790)	-0.162** (0.0783)	-0.0331 (0.0741)	-0.164** (0.0687)	-0.177** (0.0800)	-0.175** (0.0792)	-0.0401 (0.0756)	-0.188*** (0.0726)
Log (Age)^2	0.0389** (0.0168)	0.0353** (0.0166)	0.0146 (0.0157)	0.0384** (0.0152)	0.0365** (0.0173)	0.0326* (0.0171)	0.0113 (0.0161)	0.0339** (0.0155)	0.0387** (0.0175)	0.0354** (0.0173)	0.0125 (0.0164)	0.0380** (0.0163)
Log (Worker)	0.776*** (0.0293)	0.731*** (0.0300)	0.758*** (0.0290)	0.749*** (0.0314)	0.782*** (0.0302)	0.738*** (0.0307)	0.766*** (0.0296)	0.758*** (0.0321)	0.779*** (0.0305)	0.737*** (0.0312)	0.764*** (0.0301)	0.772*** (0.0345)
Log (Worker)^2	0.0154*** (0.00564)	0.0223*** (0.00571)	0.0226*** (0.00579)	0.0186*** (0.00592)	0.0141** (0.00579)	0.0212*** (0.00584)	0.0219*** (0.00590)	0.0174*** (0.00596)	0.0153*** (0.00590)	0.0220*** (0.00596)	0.0228*** (0.00602)	0.0149** (0.00653)
Alternative energy	0.189*** (0.0457)	0.189*** (0.0457)	0.161*** (0.0461)	0.263*** (0.0606)	0.179*** (0.0469)	0.178*** (0.0469)	0.154*** (0.0474)	0.248*** (0.0578)	0.156*** (0.0476)	0.157*** (0.0476)	0.146*** (0.0482)	0.284*** (0.0682)
Innovation	0.0754 (0.0507)	0.0393 (0.0511)	0.0397 (0.0503)	0.0616 (0.0516)	0.0814 (0.0522)	0.0491 (0.0525)	0.0493 (0.0517)	0.0710 (0.0526)	0.0862 (0.0530)	0.0543 (0.0532)	0.0538 (0.0525)	0.0798 (0.0553)
R&D	0.197*** (0.0692)	0.195*** (0.0688)	0.193*** (0.0712)	0.210*** (0.0705)	0.192*** (0.0724)	0.187*** (0.0720)	0.179** (0.0749)	0.186** (0.0726)	0.200*** (0.0743)	0.194*** (0.0739)	0.185** (0.0768)	0.187** (0.0774)
Financial access	0.234*** (0.0370)	0.242*** (0.0365)	0.206*** (0.0366)	0.261*** (0.0376)	0.251*** (0.0382)	0.255*** (0.0377)	0.207*** (0.0375)	0.257*** (0.0369)	0.255*** (0.0388)	0.259*** (0.0382)	0.203*** (0.0380)	0.295*** (0.0413)
Credit access	0.0702* (0.0362)	0.0720** (0.0358)	0.0606* (0.0350)	0.0885** (0.0370)	0.0823** (0.0372)	0.0841** (0.0368)	0.0756** (0.0359)	0.0967*** (0.0373)	0.0793** (0.0377)	0.0810** (0.0373)	0.0822** (0.0364)	0.0937** (0.0390)
Competition	0.0521 (0.0337)	0.0439 (0.0332)	-0.0726** (0.0329)	0.125** (0.0571)	0.0539 (0.0344)	0.0437 (0.0339)	-0.0757** (0.0339)	0.0826** (0.0402)	0.0445 (0.0357)	0.0373 (0.0352)	-0.0771** (0.0349)	0.209*** (0.0759)
Industry dummies	NO	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES
Regional dummies	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
First-stage F value				117.732				231.377				75.478
Observations	5,481	5,481	5,481	5,481	5,211	5,211	5,211	5,211	5,098	5,098	5,098	5,098
R-square	0.662	0.670	0.711	0.661	0.663	0.670	0.712	0.665	0.663	0.671	0.712	0.639

Notes: The dependent variable is the natural logarithm of sales in 2014. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. ***, ** and * significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% levels, respectively.

APPENDIX

Appendix Table A1. NUTS II- and NUTS III-level classification of Turkish provinces.			
NUTS II	NUTS II code	NUTS III - province	NUTS III code
Istanbul Subregion	TR10	Istanbul	TR100
Tekirdağ Subregion	TR21	Tekirdağ	TR211
		Edirne	TR212
		Kırklareli	TR213
Balıkesir subregion	TR22	Balıkesir	TR221
		Çanakkale	TR222
Izmir Subregion	TR31	İzmir	TR310
Aydın Subregion	TR32	Aydın	TR321
		Denizli	TR322
		Muğla	TR323
Manisa Subregion	TR33	Manisa	TR331
		Afyonkarahisar	TR332
		Kütahya	TR333
		Uşak	TR334
Bursa Subregion	TR41	Bursa	TR411
		Eskişehir	TR412
		Bilecik	TR413
Kocaeli Subregion	TR42	Kocaeli	TR421
		Sakarya	TR422
		Düzce	TR423
		Bolu	TR424
		Yalova	TR425
Ankara Subregion	TR51	Ankara	TR510
Konya Subregion	TR52	Konya	TR521
		Karaman	TR522
Antalya Subregion	TR61	Antalya	TR611
		Isparta	TR612
		Burdur	TR613
Adana Subregion	TR62	Adana	TR621
		Mersin	TR622
Hatay Subregion	TR63	Hatay	TR631
		Kahramanmaraş	TR632
		Osmaniye	TR633
Kırıkkale Subregion	TR71	Kırıkkale	TR711
		Aksaray	TR712
		Niğde	TR713
		Nevşehir	TR714
		Kırşehir	TR715
Kayseri Subregion	TR72	Kayseri	TR721

		Sivas	TR722
		Yozgat	TR723
Zonguldak Subregion	TR81	Zonguldak	TR811
		Karabük	TR812
		Bartın	TR813
Kastamonu Subregion	TR82	Kastamonu	TR821
		Çankırı	TR822
		Sinop	TR823
Samsun Subregion	TR83	Samsun	TR831
		Tokat	TR832
		Çorum	TR833
		Amasya	TR834
Trabzon Subregion	TR90	Trabzon	TR901
		Ordu	TR902
		Giresun	TR903
		Rize	TR904
		Artvin	TR905
		Gümüşhane	TR906
Erzurum Subregion	TRA1	Erzurum	TRA11
		Erzincan	TRA12
		Bayburt	TRA13
Ağrı Subregion	TRA2	Ağrı	TRA21
		Kars	TRA22
		İğdır	TRA23
		Ardahan	TRA24
Malatya Subregion	TRB1	Malatya	TRB11
		Elazığ	TRB12
		Bingöl	TRB13
		Tunceli	TRB14
Van Subregion	TRB2	Van	TRB21
		Muş	TRB22
		Bitlis	TRB23
		Hakkâri	TRB24
Gaziantep Subregion	TRC1	Gaziantep	TRC11
		Adıyaman	TRC12
		Kilis	TRC13
Şanlıurfa Subregion	TRC2	Şanlıurfa	TRC21
		Diyarbakır	TRC22
Mardin Subregion	TRC3	Mardin	TRC31
		Batman	TRC32
		Şırnak	TRC33
		Siirt	TRC34

Appendix Table A2. Construction of firm-specific variables from the World Bank Enterprise Survey data set	
Variables	Questionnaires used for the construction of the variables and variable description
Sales	D2: In fiscal year 2014, what were this establishment's total annual sales for ALL products and services? Sales: The natural logarithm of total annual sales in 2014.
PO dummy	C6: Over fiscal year 2014, did this establishment experience power outages? PO dummy: A dummy variable is constructed which equals to one if firm experienced power outage and zero otherwise.
PO frequency	C7: In a typical month, over fiscal year 2014, how many power outages did this establishment experience? PO Frequency: The frequency of times firm experienced power outage
PO duration	C8: How long did these power outages last on average? (C8a: Hours and C8b: Minutes) PO Duration: Average duration of a power outage (measured in hours)
Size	L1: Number of full-time employees in 2014 Size: The natural logarithm of the number of full-time employees in 2014.
Age	B.5: In what year did this establishment begin operations? which is subtracted from the year of survey Age: The natural logarithm of the firm's age.
Foreign ownership	b2b: Private foreign individuals-% Foreign: A dummy variable that equals to one if firm has some foreign ownership
Export	d3c: Direct exports - % Export: A dummy variable which is equal to one if a firm's sales include direct exports.
Sole ownership	B.3: What percentage of this firm does the largest owner or owners own? Sole ownership: A dummy variable which is equal to one if a firm is owned by one individual and zero otherwise
Manager experience	B.7 How many years of experience working in this sector does the Top Manager have? Manager experience: The natural logarithm of the year of experience the top manager has in the same sector
Manager education	TU_B.7b: What is the highest educational degree the top manager has completed/obtained? Manager education: This is a categorical variable taking value 0, 1, 2, 3 and 4 if the top manager has no, primary school, secondary/high school, university and postgraduate (Master's and Ph.D.) degree, respectively.
Alternative energy	C10: Over the course of fiscal year [insert last complete fiscal year], did this establishment own or share a generator? TUC_6: In fiscal year 2014, what percentage of this establishment's electricity came from a solar installation or alternative energy source that the establishment owned or shared? Alternative energy: A dummy variable that equals one if a firm either owns a generator or firm's electricity came from a solar installation or alternative energy source.
Innovation	H.1: During the last three years, has this establishment introduced new or significantly improved products or services? Innovation: A dummy variable that equals to one if a firm introduced new or significantly improved products or services.
R&D	H.7: During the last three years, did this establishment spend on formal research and development activities, either in-house or contracted with other companies, excluding market research surveys? R&D: A dummy variable that equals to one if a firm spend on formal research and development activities, either in-house or contracted with other companies, excluding market research surveys.
Financial access	K.7: At this time, does this establishment have an overdraft facility? Financial access: A dummy variable that equals to one if a firm has an overdraft facility.
Credit access	K.8: At this time, does this establishment have a line of credit or a loan from a financial institution?

	Credit access: A dummy variable that equals to one if a firm has a line of credit or a loan from a financial institution.
Competition	E.11: Does this establishment compete against unregistered or informal firms? Competition: A dummy variable that equals to one if a firm competes against unregistered or informal firms.

Appendix Table A3. Descriptions and sources of electoral and regional control variables.		
Variable	Description	Source
AKP vote share	% of votes for the AKP in 2011 parliamentary elections	Turkish Statistical Institute
Electoral competition	Negative absolute value of the vote difference between the incumbent party and its main challenger in each NUTS II region in 2011 parliamentary election where higher value represents higher electoral competition.	Own calculations based on data from Turkish Statistical Institute
Close competitor	Interaction between close race variable and a dummy variable, which is equal to one when the AKP's main competitor is any other right-wing party (e.g., MHP)	Own calculations based on data from Turkish Statistical Institute
Gross domestic product (GDP) per capita	This variable is the natural logarithm of the GDP per capita.	Turkish Statistical Institute Regional Database
Public investment	The natural logarithm of total amount of public investment to each NUTS II region per 1000 people in 2012 prices	Ministry of Development
Population	The natural logarithm of the regional population	Turkish Statistical Institute Regional Database
Rural population	The percentage of rural population	Turkish Statistical Institute Regional Database
Electricity consumption	The natural logarithm of the regional energy use, measured in million watt-hours	Turkish Statistical Institute Regional Database

Table A4. Descriptive Statistics.					
Variable	Observation	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
PO dummy	5,949	0.42	0.49	0	1
PO frequency	5,650	1.47	4.47	0	100
PO duration	5,523	1.04	3.82	0	100
log(Sales in 2014)	5,795	12.96	1.86	8.21	25.61
Full-time workers in 2014	5,986	32.43	298.17	1	22000
Manager experience	5,944	19.85	10.73	1	68
Manager education	5,963	1.98	0.69	0	4
Sole ownership	5,933	0.80	0.40	0	1
Foreign ownership	6,006	0.01	0.11	0	1
Export	5,950	0.06	0.24	0	1
Age	5,974	14.27	11.76	1	159
Alternative energy	5,999	0.17	0.38	0	1
Innovation	6,003	0.12	0.33	0	1
R&D	6,003	0.06	0.24	0	1
Financial access	6003	0.35	0.48	0	1
Credit access	6,003	0.30	0.46	0	1
Competition	5,912	0.27	0.44	0	1
AKP vote share	26	50.70	10.90	32.54	68.31
Electoral competition	26	-25.90	16.57	-54.64	-0.46
Close competitor	26	-9.05	19.14	-54.64	0.00
log (GDP per capita)	26	9.82	0.37	9.20	10.58
log (Public investment per 1000)	26	5.69	0.38	5.11	6.47
Rural	26	22.34	13.16	1.04	50.61
log(Population)	26	14.70	0.59	13.53	16.46
log (Electricity consumption)	26	15.50	0.89	13.60	17.34

Table A5. Determinants of power outage measure					
	PO dummy	PO frequency		PO duration	
	1	2	3	4	5
	Probit	ZTP	ZINBR	ZTP	ZINBR
AKP vote share	-0.0122***	-0.0224***	-0.0300***	-0.00595***	-0.00758
	(0.00201)	(0.00144)	(0.00421)	(0.00169)	(0.00543)
Log (Worker)	0.193***	0.144***	0.149**	0.161***	0.132
	(0.0365)	(0.0264)	(0.0677)	(0.0333)	(0.0889)
Log (Worker)^2	-0.0335***	-0.0131***	-0.00675	-0.0260***	-0.0259*
	(0.00701)	(0.00464)	(0.0115)	(0.00619)	(0.0151)
Alternative energy	0.475***	0.129***	0.108	-0.401***	-0.343***
	(0.0530)	(0.0287)	(0.0841)	(0.0455)	(0.120)
GDP per capita	0.944***	-1.392***	-1.835***	-0.319***	-1.152***
	(0.0887)	(0.0591)	(0.184)	(0.0809)	(0.307)
Public investment per 1000 people	-0.156**	0.180***	0.140	-0.392***	-0.633***
	(0.0642)	(0.0468)	(0.140)	(0.0754)	(0.204)
Rural	0.0234***	0.00839***	0.00871	0.0413***	0.0379***
	(0.00261)	(0.00170)	(0.00538)	(0.00229)	(0.00718)
log (Population)	0.608***	-0.398***	-0.691***	-0.224***	-0.668***
	(0.0490)	(0.0334)	(0.0929)	(0.0397)	(0.138)
log (Energy)	-0.315***	0.587***	0.774***	0.808***	1.449***
	(0.0608)	(0.0376)	(0.120)	(0.0580)	(0.191)
Log-likelihood	-3540.48	-6858.359	-4346.9554	-6107.4632	-3055.92
Wald test of exogeneity (Chi-square)					
P-value of the exogeneity test					
LR test of alpha			5022.81		6103.08
P-value of LR test			0.0000		0.0000
Observations	5,931	2,158	2,158	2,083	2,083

Notes: Industry dummies and constant are included in all regression but are not reported. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. ***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% level, respectively.

Table A6. Re-estimation of Table 1 when AKP vote share, electoral competition and close competitor variables included simultaneously

	PO dummy	PO Frequency	PO frequency	PO Duration	PO duration
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(5)	(6)
Variables	IVProbit	IV-ZTP	IV-ZINBR	IV-ZTP	IV-ZINBR
AKP vote share	-0.0191*** (0.00417)	-0.00527* (0.00308)	-0.00411 (0.00955)	-0.00896 (0.00558)	-0.000595 (0.0149)
Electoral competition	-0.00337 (0.00310)	0.0178*** (0.00235)	0.0226*** (0.00691)	0.0166*** (0.00226)	0.0218*** (0.00716)
Close competitor	-0.00374** (0.00159)	-0.00301** (0.00129)	-0.00162 (0.00344)	-0.000735 (0.00144)	-0.00194 (0.00412)
Log (Worker)	0.191*** (0.0365)	0.153*** (0.0265)	0.165** (0.0675)	0.159*** (0.0334)	0.147 (0.0894)
Log (Worker) ²	-0.0332*** (0.00700)	-0.0147*** (0.00464)	-0.0107 (0.0115)	-0.0256*** (0.00620)	-0.0277* (0.0152)
Alternative energy	0.479*** (0.0530)	0.136*** (0.0287)	0.138 (0.0843)	-0.405*** (0.0455)	-0.358*** (0.121)
GDP per capita	0.858*** (0.0946)	-1.270*** (0.0646)	-1.692*** (0.199)	-0.468*** (0.0918)	-1.307*** (0.326)
Public investment per 1000 people	-0.0971 (0.0682)	0.239*** (0.0494)	0.173 (0.144)	-0.358*** (0.0780)	-0.469** (0.222)
Rural	0.0267*** (0.00323)	-0.00427* (0.00242)	-0.00294 (0.00661)	0.0489*** (0.00322)	0.0413*** (0.00839)
log (Population)	0.648*** (0.0539)	-0.562*** (0.0413)	-0.900*** (0.115)	-0.0891 (0.0574)	-0.619*** (0.159)
log (Energy)	-0.231*** (0.0688)	0.491*** (0.0426)	0.703*** (0.132)	0.902*** (0.0659)	1.599*** (0.210)
Log-likelihood	-3520.3589	-6828.0711	-4341.5846	-6101.0636	-3054.2316
Wald test of exogeneity (Chi-square)	42.73				
P-value of the exogeneity test	0.0000				
LR test of alpha			4972.97		6093.66
P-value of LR test			0.0000		0.0000
Joint significance (Chi-square)	41.76	61.02	10.89	57.7	9.31
p-value	0.0000	0.0000	0.0043	0.0000	0.0095
Observations	5,931	2,158	2,158	2,083	2,083
Notes: Industry dummies and constant are included in all regression but are not reported. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. ***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% level, respectively.					

Table A7. Determinants of power outage measures when regional control variables are excluded from the analysis						
VARIABLES	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
AKP vote share	-0.0209***	-0.0608***	-0.0112*			
	(0.00200)	(0.00452)	(0.00591)			
Electoral competition				0.0196***	0.0255***	0.0105***
				(0.00138)	(0.00313)	(0.00387)
Close competitor				-0.00296**	-0.00962***	-0.00241
				(0.00132)	(0.00339)	(0.00407)
Log (Worker)	0.159***	0.281***	0.153*	0.174***	0.313***	0.149*
	(0.0361)	(0.0730)	(0.0890)	(0.0363)	(0.0777)	(0.0887)
Log (Worker)^2	-0.0279***	-0.0355***	-0.0273*	-0.0291***	-0.0442***	-0.0260*
	(0.00698)	(0.0124)	(0.0150)	(0.00701)	(0.0132)	(0.0150)
Alternative energy	0.549***	0.0953	-0.517***	0.514***	0.177*	-0.508***
	(0.0513)	(0.0910)	(0.118)	(0.0518)	(0.0976)	(0.117)
Log-likelihood	-3755.24	-4474.04	-3117.32	-3712.73	-4527.68	-3115.12
Wald test of exogeneity (Chi-square)	3.66					
P-value of the exogeneity test	0.0556					
LR test of alpha=0		5537.83	6598.25		6040.36	6571.49
P-value LR test		0.0000	0.0000		0.0000	0.0000
Joint significance (Chi-square)				249.88	69.30	8.92
p-value (Joint significance)				0.0000	0.0000	0.0116
Observations	5,931	2,158	2,083	5,931	2,158	2,083
Notes: Industry dummies and constant are included in all regression but are not reported. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. ***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% level, respectively. Dependent variables in column (1), (2) and (3) are PO dummy, PO frequency and PO duration where IV-Probit, IV-ZINBR and IV-ZINBR models are used, respectively. Dependent variables in columns (4), (5) and (6) are PO dummy, PO frequency and PO duration where Probit, ZINBR and ZINBR models are used, respectively.						

Table A8. Re-estimation of Table 1 when electoral variables are obtained by using 2002, 2007 and 2011 parliamentary elections										
	H1: Core hypothesis					H2 & H3: Swing hypothesis				
	PO dummy	PO frequency		PO duration		PO dummy	PO frequency		PO duration	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
	Probit IV	ZTP-IV	ZINBR - IV	ZTP-IV	ZINBR - IV	Probit	ZTP	ZINBR	ZTP	ZINBR
AKP vote share (02-07-11)	-0.0166*** (0.00228)	-0.0284*** (0.00153)	-0.0349*** (0.00437)	-0.00775*** (0.00186)	-0.00995* (0.00586)					
Electoral competition (02-07-11)						0.00961*** (0.00189)	0.0236*** (0.00143)	0.0275*** (0.00379)	0.00604*** (0.00141)	0.00750* (0.00415)
Close competitor (02-07-11)						-0.00261 (0.00172)	-0.00323** (0.00140)	-0.00214 (0.00366)	0.000541 (0.00157)	-0.00135 (0.00449)
Log (Worker)	0.195*** (0.0365)	0.148*** (0.0264)	0.151** (0.0670)	0.148*** (0.0326)	0.154* (0.0890)	0.195*** (0.0365)	0.151*** (0.0264)	0.160** (0.0671)	0.148*** (0.0326)	0.151* (0.0889)
Log (Worker)^2	-0.0336*** (0.00701)	-0.0129*** (0.00464)	-0.00684 (0.0114)	-0.0223*** (0.00601)	-0.0274* (0.0150)	-0.0336*** (0.00701)	-0.0144*** (0.00463)	-0.0104 (0.0114)	-0.0222*** (0.00600)	-0.0266* (0.0150)
Alternative energy	0.472*** (0.0530)	0.127*** (0.0287)	0.104 (0.0833)	-0.410*** (0.0445)	-0.514*** (0.118)	0.475*** (0.0530)	0.134*** (0.0287)	0.140* (0.0838)	-0.420*** (0.0447)	-0.512*** (0.118)
GDP per capita	0.911*** (0.0890)	-1.433*** (0.0593)	-1.852*** (0.183)	-0.313*** (0.0813)	-1.173*** (0.306)	0.933*** (0.0928)	-1.231*** (0.0608)	-1.681*** (0.190)	-0.414*** (0.0841)	-1.313*** (0.314)
Public investment per 1000 people	-0.153** (0.0639)	0.142*** (0.0453)	0.0987 (0.133)	-0.310*** (0.0710)	-0.584*** (0.201)	-0.156** (0.0670)	0.228*** (0.0479)	0.173 (0.140)	-0.353*** (0.0763)	-0.409* (0.214)
Rural	0.0196*** (0.00272)	0.00154 (0.00177)	0.00237 (0.00540)	0.0412*** (0.00233)	0.0382*** (0.00729)	0.0207*** (0.00283)	-0.00502*** (0.00188)	-0.00246 (0.00563)	0.0448*** (0.00252)	0.0409*** (0.00755)
log (Population)	0.611*** (0.0484)	-0.390*** (0.0335)	-0.642*** (0.0922)	-0.232*** (0.0394)	-0.695*** (0.138)	0.546*** (0.0539)	-0.644*** (0.0367)	-0.970*** (0.1000)	-0.150*** (0.0456)	-0.643*** (0.148)
log (Energy consumption)	-0.347*** (0.0609)	0.514*** (0.0371)	0.676*** (0.119)	0.828*** (0.0578)	1.492*** (0.190)	-0.298*** (0.0657)	0.539*** (0.0382)	0.779*** (0.127)	0.862*** (0.0632)	1.632*** (0.204)
Log-likelihood	-3531.142	-6809.4317	-4340.475	-6113.9131	-3056.58	-3545.09	-6814.97	-4339.92	-6103.69	-3053.74
Wald test of exogeneity (Chi-square)	10.82									
P-value of the exogeneity test	0.0010									
LR test of alpha=0			4937.91		6114.66			4950.09		6099.9
P-value of LR test			0.0000		0.0000			0.0000		0.0000
Joint significance (Chi-square)						27.6	323.19	66.70	28.25	4.03
p-value (Joint significance)						0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.1336
Observations	5,931	2,158	2,158	2,083	2,083	5,931	2,158	2,158	2,083	2,083

Notes: Industry dummies and constant are included in all regression but are not reported. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. ***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% level, respectively. Results in columns (1)-(5) obtained with the use of instrumental variable (IV) estimation where AKP vote shares are instrumented with the shift-share instrumental variable.

Table A9. Determinants of firm performance when sales growth used as dependent variable			
	(1)	(2)	(3)
VARIABLES	PO dummy	PO Frequency	PO duration
PO variable	-0.287**	-0.166***	-0.356***
	(0.114)	(0.0551)	(0.120)
Log (Sales in 2012)	-0.127***	-0.123***	-0.124***
	(0.00821)	(0.00792)	(0.00860)
Manager experience	0.0228	0.0170	0.0201
	(0.0148)	(0.0146)	(0.0156)
Manager education	0.0108	0.00507	0.00918
	(0.0130)	(0.0129)	(0.0140)
Sole owner	-0.0611***	-0.0638***	-0.0491*
	(0.0232)	(0.0235)	(0.0267)
Foreign owner	-0.0444	-0.0537	-0.0110
	(0.0920)	(0.0948)	(0.102)
Export	0.0771**	0.0643*	0.0796**
	(0.0360)	(0.0357)	(0.0389)
Log (Age)	-0.233***	-0.224***	-0.255***
	(0.0625)	(0.0625)	(0.0681)
Log (Age)^2	0.0426***	0.0411***	0.0468***
	(0.0125)	(0.0125)	(0.0136)
Log (Worker)	0.0853***	0.0893***	0.0919***
	(0.0185)	(0.0183)	(0.0201)
Log (Worker)^2	0.000029	-0.000757	-0.00138
	(0.00307)	(0.00305)	(0.00338)
Alternative energy	0.0619*	0.0559*	0.0757**
	(0.0343)	(0.0313)	(0.0371)
Innovation	0.0672**	0.0842***	0.0759***
	(0.0272)	(0.0277)	(0.0291)
R&D	0.0294	0.0183	0.00768
	(0.0391)	(0.0389)	(0.0422)
Financial access	0.0651***	0.0490**	0.0771***
	(0.0204)	(0.0193)	(0.0232)
Credit access	0.0425**	0.0368*	0.0307
	(0.0196)	(0.0195)	(0.0205)
Competition	0.167***	0.137***	0.210***
	(0.0300)	(0.0210)	(0.0407)
First-stage F-value	94.3573	175.36	57.558
Observations	4,349	4,213	4,129

Notes: Dependent variable is the sales growth between 2012 and 2014. The results are obtained with the use of 2SLS regressions. Robust standard errors are shown in parenthesis. ***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% levels, respectively.

Figure A1. Frequency distribution of the number of power outages experienced by firms

Figure A2. Frequency distribution of the average power outage durations experienced by firms (measured in hours)